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**Inter-human Relationship
in an Interdependent World**

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The Editor, *Jnanadeepa*, Jnana Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune 411014, India Tel (office): +91-20-27034968, (res): +91-20-27034169 Fax: +91-20-27034801

E - mail: <kurusj@gmail.com>
<jdv@vsnl.com>

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Editorial

The theme we have chosen for this issue of *Jnanadeepa* is: **Inter-human Relationships in an Interdependent world**. The issue explores the contribution which different religions and disciplines can make to the shaping of human life and relationships in a world which is becoming increasingly more aware of the interconnectedness and interdependence of all things.

There are two articles in this issue which discuss the contribution Indian religions can make to the structuring of human life and relationships in today's world. The first deals with Bhagavad Gita's message of harmony in an interdependent world. The mystical insights of the Gita enable us to look at the world as a divine abode, as a divine body, as a divine process and a divine dharma. For the Gita the world is a reality of interconnectedness. Such a vision of the world brings with it the human responsibility to promote this interrelationality in a harmonious process. We need to become aware that there is a deep bond between humans and the things of nature and take responsibility for the preservation of the integrity of creation and the promotion of harmony in society. The second discusses the folk religious world-view and points out how folk religions create and affirm the interrelationships not only between human beings in society but also between humans, nature and the supernatural powers. The folk religions have the potential to question and subvert the unjust and discriminatory elements in our caste-based society. They can also positively orient humans to care for nature and not to exploit it for selfish purposes. Thus they can make a significant contribution to the creation of a just, egalitarian and eco-friendly society.

There are three articles in this issue which develop Christian perspectives on interhuman relationships. The first deals with the significance of the Christian faith in the Triune God for our life in society. The author believes that the Trinity is a theological representation of interrelatedness in the human and cosmic community and that it is a model of humanistic and inter-religious trilogue. He also points out that the Trinity provides an alternative paradigm of power in church and society. The second deals with Jesus Christ and shows how Jesus' way of being human is a challenge to authentic human unfolding through interrelationships. Jesus has revealed to us the mystery of human existence on earth and taught through his life that self-emptying love is

the heart of human interrelationship. The third discusses the parable of the Good Samaritan in Luke 10:29-37. After dealing with the love commandments of Jesus in a general way, the article shows that in this parable the neighbour is defined from the perspective of the one in need. Hence the command to love the neighbour has a universal application since all humans are in a sense people in need. Besides, the love commandment is present, in one form or another, in all religious traditions. Hence it can serve as a firm basis for interreligious dialogue and collaboration.

There is an article in this issue which discusses the significance and implications of feminism in an interdependent world. It points out that feminism as a movement and a way of life emphasizes values like mutuality, co-responsibility and partnership leading to genuine interdependence between men and women. Building on the theme of interdependence, feminism from the grassroots argues that stories of women's agency and resistance are crucial in understanding the world of today. And this calls for an attentive listening to these stories.

Finally, there is an article which makes scientific and anthropological reflections on reality as relationality. Basing himself on the findings of modern science about reality and the human self, the author contends that the world is a network of interrelated entities. Because of development beyond our control, we are unable to publish now some articles from other disciplines like psychology and sociology which were originally planned for this issue.

However, included in this issue are two articles on development which were originally meant for the last issue. The first offers some Christian reflections on development. Basing himself on the Christian tradition and taking into account the social teaching of the Church, the author develops some Christian perspectives on development. The second deals with the role of the Church in the development of Goa. There has been a progressive abandonment of the Portuguese legacy. The post-colonial Church in Goa has made a renewed commitment to the promotion of the development of the State and expressed its readiness to be an active partner in the collaborative effort for regeneration. The Church believes that it is her sacred duty towards humanity to help in the integral development of the human person and human society. This is certainly a progressive step.

Kurien Kunnumpuram, SJ
Editor